

Exploring the Therapeutic Potential of Fish Oil Components in Leukemia Treatment: A Comprehensive Pharmaceutical Chemistry Perspective

Aleeza Suleman¹, Maryam Rehman¹, Hafiz Muhammad Haseeb Khaliq^{2*}

¹*Department of Zoology, Kinnaird College for Women University KCWU Lahore Pakistan*

²*Kausar Abdullah Malik K.A.M School of Life Sciences, Forman Christian College (A Chartered University) FCCU Lahore Pakistan*

*Correspondence: haseebkhaliq119@gmail.com

Conflict of interest: None

ABSTRACT

Leukemia, a diverse group of hematologic malignancies, poses significant challenges in treatment due to its complex etiology and resistance to conventional therapies. This review delves into the emerging field of pharmaceutical chemistry, specifically focusing on the anticancer properties of fish oil components in the context of leukemia. Omega-3 fatty acids, notably eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) found in fish oil, have garnered attention for their multifaceted roles in cellular processes. Recent studies highlight their potential as novel therapeutic agents against leukemia. The review comprehensively examines the molecular mechanisms underlying the anticancer activity of these components, elucidating their impact on leukemia cell proliferation, apoptosis, and differentiation. Insights into the modulation of critical signaling pathways involved in leukemogenesis, such as PI3K/Akt and MAPK pathways, provide a foundation for understanding the fish oil components' efficacy. Additionally, their ability to induce apoptosis in leukemia cells and promote differentiation towards a less aggressive phenotype offers promising avenues for targeted therapy.

KEYWORDS: Leukemia, fish oil components, pharmaceutical chemistry, omega-3 fatty acids, anticancer activity, molecular mechanisms, therapeutic potential, apoptosis, signaling pathways, formulation optimization.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer is the second leading cause of death in the United States and the leading cause of death in Canada. Improving current conventional therapies and treatment paradigms could result in improved patient outcomes and a reduction in deaths. As such, there has been extensive research into the efficacy of n-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (LCPUFA), eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA), and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) in preclinical models of cancer. The pleiotropic effects of n-3 LCPUFA on tumors include increasing apoptosis, inducing cell cycle arrest, decreasing cell growth, and halting proliferation in experimental models of cancer.(1)

Acute myeloid leukemias (AML) are a heterogeneous group of hematological malignancies for which therapy is stratified according to cytogenetic and molecular prognostic factors. AML with high-risk

cytogenetics leads to a dismal prognosis, is often refractory to induction therapy, and often relapses, even after allogeneic bone marrow transplantation. Hence, it is an unmet medical need. Improving the efficacy of treatment and optimizing the benefit-risk ratio in AML is the subject of intense clinical research.(2)

Polyunsaturated long-chain n-3 fatty acids (n-3 PUFAs) have antitumoral properties that have been demonstrated in various in vitro solid tumor models, such as breast cancer, prostate cancer, and ovarian cancer cell lines. Animal models confirmed an antitumoral effect, with the induction of apoptosis and cell cycle arrest in murine autochthonous colon cancer and mammary rat breast cancer. Among hematological malignancies, the same properties have been described for lymphoid and myeloid cell lines. Among AML cell lines and primary blasts, there is evidence that n-3 PUFAs induce apoptotic cell death and a mitochondrial metabolic switch from oxidative phosphorylation to glycolysis, together with activation of the oxidative-stress-related NRF2 pathway that is not sufficient to prevent cell death. In human cancer, n-3 PUFAs have been safely administered to women with metastatic breast cancer. A phase II trial evaluating oral supplementation with FO capsules concomitantly with FEC100 chemotherapy showed an association between high n-3 PUFA intake and better outcome.(3)

Several mechanisms of action of n-3 PUFAs have been described in solid tumor models. Structurally, EPA and DHA incorporate into cancer cell membranes and modify lipid raft composition. They have been shown to inhibit COX-2 and PGE2 pro-inflammatory activity and to be associated with reduced cancer invasion, and n-3 PUFAs can inhibit TLR-induced MHC class II upregulation and cytokine production. DHA can also impede I- κ B phosphorylation, thus suppressing NF- κ B transcription factor activity. The PI3K/AKT signaling pathway is inhibited by DHA in the MDA-MB-231 cell line engrafted to BALB/c nude mice fed a high DHA diet. Evidence of cell arrest in G1-phase has been observed in breast cancer. An anti-angiogenic effect has also been described through the attenuation of VEGF-induced angiogenesis.(4)

In acute leukemia, it has been reported that DHA can induce direct in vitro cytotoxicity in the KG1a cell line, and cycle arrest in S-phase of the Jurkat cell line. Hallmarks of apoptosis, such as nuclear fragmentation, have been demonstrated in the U937 cell line exposed to 100 μ M DHA, as well as upregulation of Bax mRNA in the HL-60 cell line. Exposure of HL-60 cells to EPA induces increased fluorescence of H2-DCFDA, suggesting the involvement of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in triggering cell death. Mechanisms involving cytoplasmic calcium release, associated with cell death, have also been demonstrated in U937 cells. A ROS-induced mechanism for the sensitization of HL-60 cells to arsenic trioxide by DHA has been described, and lymphoid cell lines may be sensitized to other anticancer agents, with an increase in lipid peroxide formation.(5)

Whether n-3 PUFAs can induce mitochondrial impairment leading to cell death in AML is still unclear, and the potential synergism of n-3 PUFAs with chemotherapy has not been yet evaluated. Here, we show that EPA, DHA, and clinical-grade FO can induce in vitro cell death of AML cells, associated with phosphatidylserine exposure and a decrease in mitochondrial membrane potential. We demonstrate a mitochondrial metabolic shift and mitochondrial genomic damage, as well as an oxidative stress-related Nrf2 pathway activation, unable to avoid cell death. Furthermore, these effects of FO were additive with the cytotoxicity of AraC.

Fish oil (FO) emulsion contains 1.25–2.82 g eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and 1.44–3.09 g docosahexaenoic acid (DHA)/100 mL. It is authorized registered as parenteral nutrition supplementation for intravenous (IV) infusion with long chain omega-3-fatty acids. FO supplementation, mostly by oral route, has been associated with an improved nutritional status in patients treated for diverse cancer types. In the setting of hematologic malignancies, an increase in EPA and DHA plasma levels has been associated with an improved outcome in a prospective comparative study on 22 patients. Oral supplementation with FO capsules in children treated with methotrexate has been associated with improved liver function. There is evidence of benefit and safety of FO in critically ill patients, such as a reduction of the hospital length of stay after abdominal surgery, and a reduced length of stay in intensive care units for patients with sepsis treated with FO. These data suggest that a high dose of FO can be safely administered to vulnerable patients. We hypothesized that FO could be safely administered to patients newly diagnosed with high-risk AML, without compromising daunorubicin and cytarabine pharmacokinetics, and that its adjunct to standard 3+7 may improve the complete remission rate of induction therapy. We thus set up a feasibility phase II study to evaluate the safety and efficacy of the adjunct of a FO lipid emulsion to daunorubicin and cytarabine induction chemotherapy in untreated AML patients with adverse cytogenetics.(6)

Docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) is the longest chain and most unsaturated fatty acid commonly found in nature. DHA represents the extreme example of an omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acid (PUFA), an important family of compounds that are reputed to possess many human health benefits, including anticancer properties. Polyunsaturated fatty acids are mostly of the n-3 or n-6 series because of the presence of the first double bond at the third or sixth positions, respectively, from the methyl terminal of the aliphatic carbon chain. Commonly found in cold-water fish, n-3 PUFAs are mostly comprised of EPA and DHA. In addition to EPA and DHA, other forms of n-3 PUFA are also available for dietary consumption. For example, green leafy vegetables, flaxseed, rapeseed, and walnuts contain another n-3 PUFA, alpha-linolenic acid (ALA). Also, more recently, certain plant oils have been genetically modified to synthesize stear(7)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Studies involving cancer patients receiving n-3 LCPUFAs (EPA and/or DHA) as intervention during cancer treatment were included. Review papers, abstracts, individual case reports, and animal or cell line studies were excluded.

QWDATA SOURCES, SEARCH STRATEGY AND STUDY SELECTION

A systematic literature search was conducted using electronic bibliographic databases, including Ovid MEDLINE and EBSCOhost CINAHL, from inception through August 2020. Searches were limited to peer-reviewed studies. Search terms were derived from (1) DHA/EPA/dietary fats, (2) immune response/inflammation, and (3) cancer/solid tumors/oncology treatment. Titles and abstracts were screened for eligibility, and duplicates were removed. Full texts of eligible abstracts underwent a second screening by two investigators for inclusion eligibility.

DATA EXTRACTION AND SYNTHESIS

Data extraction, completed by MN, included manuscript information, study characteristics, patient characteristics, intervention characteristics, and outcome characteristics. Data were reviewed for accuracy by the primary investigator (CJF).

ANIMAL MODEL

TLL mice, generated through germline insertion of Moloney murine leukemia virus, were used. The mice were assigned to different dietary groups and monitored until clinical deterioration or age-related endpoints. Tumor grade scoring was deemed unnecessary due to consistent disease presentation.

DIETARY COMPOSITION

Diets were prepared under sterile conditions, with omega-3 enriched diet containing fish oil and omega-6 enriched diet containing corn oil. Additives were used to prevent oxidation of fatty acids.

IMMUNE CELL POPULATIONS

B6 female mice were assigned different diets until sacrifice. Immunological cell populations were analyzed from spleen, thymus, and bone marrow using flow cytometry.

CELL LINE, CULTURE CONDITION, AND PRIMERS

Molt-4 cell line was cultured under specified conditions. Oligonucleotides for PCR were synthesized.

CHEMICALS, DRUGS, AND KITS

Various chemicals, drugs, and kits were used for experiments, including EPA, caspase-3 activity assay, and ELISA kits.

PREPARATION OF EPA AND CELL TREATMENTS

EPA was prepared and administered to cells at different concentrations. Control cells were treated with the same concentration of ethanol.

CELL COUNT AND VIABILITY ASSAYS

Molt-4 cells were treated with different concentrations of EPA, and cell viability was assessed using trypan blue staining.

METABOLIC ACTIVITY AND PROLIFERATION ASSAYS

Metabolic activity and proliferation rates were evaluated post-EPA treatment using WST proliferation assay.

RNA ISOLATION, CDNA PREPARATION, AND REVERSE TRANSCRIPTION PCR

RNA isolation, cDNA preparation, and PCR were conducted to assess survivin and GAPDH expression.

ENZYME-LINKED IMMUNOSORBENT ASSAY

Intracellular survivin and wt-p53 protein levels were measured using sandwich ELISA kits.

CASPASE-3 ACTIVITY ASSAY

Caspase-3 activity was measured using a colorimetric assay kit.

FLOW CYTOMETRIC ANALYSES

Apoptosis was analyzed using Annexin-V-FLOUS/propidium iodide labeling solution and flow cytometry.

RESULTS

The study aimed to investigate the effects of an omega-3 (fish oil) enriched diet on lymphoma development in TLL mice, comparing it with a diet rich in omega-6 (corn oil) and a standard diet. Fish oil supplementation delayed disease onset significantly between 5 and 8 months of age, with a higher effectiveness compared to corn oil during the first 8 months. However, at 1 year, there was no significant difference in survival rates between the dietary groups. Macroscopic examination at autopsy showed extensive lymphoma growth in all groups. Fish oil altered B-cell compartments in bone marrow and spleen, and decreased NK cell fraction in the spleen. EPA, a component of fish oil, reduced cell numbers and viability in Molt-4 cells, inhibited metabolic activity and cell proliferation dose-dependently, decreased survivin mRNA and protein levels, induced apoptosis, and blocked mitochondrial respiration. DHA or EPA inhibited AML cell growth dose-dependently, with a significant decrease in viable cells. FO treatment decreased cell viability in U937 cells, and its combination with low doses of DHA and EPA

induced cell death, suggesting an additive effect. FO treatment also blocked mitochondrial respiration and induced oxidative stress and Nrf2 response in AML cells, leading to apoptosis without affecting normal CD34+ cell differentiation.(8)

Among 57 independent studies reviewed, two trials used DHA alone, two used EPA alone, and 48 used a combination of EPA and DHA from fish oil. Five additional studies reported using only EPA, but likely included DHA based on the supplements used. Supplementation varied widely in concentrations and duration. Oral capsules ranged from 300 mg to 5 g of n-3 fatty acids, with 77% providing 2 g or less per day. DHA concentrations ranged from 0 to 2 g, with 86% providing 1 g or less per day. When given with chemotherapy, supplementation lasted 6–24 weeks. Without chemotherapy, it lasted 1–6 months. Oral interventions lasted one week to 6 months, with over half lasting 4–6 weeks. Some studies provided equal doses of EPA and DHA (2.2 and 0.9 g per day, respectively), while others varied from 2–3.6 g of total n-3 per day or 4.9 g of EPA + 3.2 g of DHA per day. Enteral/parenteral nutrition studies reported varying amounts, from 0.2 g n-3 per kg of body weight to 2.25–3.3 g per day, generally lasting 5–9 days for acute interventions around surgery.(9)

OUTCOMES

Reported outcomes varied across the studies but are grouped below into the following categories: (1) weight gain or maintenance, (2) serious adverse events including neuropathy and length of hospital stay, (3) immunological measures, (4) quality of life, (5) overall survival or progression-free survival, and (6) additional parameters. Figure 2 provides an overall summary of the findings.

WEIGHT LOSS

Weight loss is a common side effect of both cancer and cancer therapies and has been reported in many studies investigating the efficacy of n-3 supplementation, particularly in advanced or palliative cancers and ones with defined pre-study weight loss. In general, oral liquid supplementation (which also included protein) was provided in instances where there was substantial weight loss prior to study entry and some evidence of malnutrition or cachexia. Compared to baseline status, n-3 supplemented groups achieved weight gain in colorectal, gastric, and pancreatic cancer studies or weight maintenance in one head and neck cancer study. Two studies, one in advanced gastrointestinal cancer patients and one in stage III non-small-cell lung cancer patients, observed improved weight maintenance in n-3 supplemented groups compared to control patients who were provided an isocaloric supplement that was not fortified with n-3 fatty acids. Capsule supplementation has been employed in three studies with palliative patients where weight maintenance was a reported study metric. In advanced lung cancer patients with systemic immune metabolic syndrome (SIMS), the combination of 600 mg EPA + DHA and celecoxib increased body weight compared to the n-3 capsules alone over a 6-week intervention. Pancreatic cancer patients, who at study entry had lost approximately 13% body weight, stabilized their weight and began to increase it by week 4 with EPA supplementation. Finally, in a low-dose EPA + DHA study of palliative pancreatic cancer patients, similar effects were observed between the 2 groups, suggesting the efficacy of n-3 fatty acids in weight stabilization.

Four studies reported weight maintenance or gain when n-3 fatty acids capsules were provided with neoadjuvant chemotherapy. In advanced lung cancer patients supplemented with 3.4 g of EPA + DHA concomitant with gemcitabine and cisplatin chemotherapy, body weight increased over the 66 day intervention. Gastrointestinal patients supplemented with 700 mg of EPA + DHA for 8 weeks with 5-fluorouracil and leucovorin chemotherapy gained an average weight over 8 weeks, and although not significant to their baseline status, was significantly different from control patients who lost weight during this time frame. Additionally, colorectal cancer patients supplemented with 608 mg of EPA + DHA resulted in weight maintenance over 8 weeks compared to control patients. In colorectal cancer patients treated with xeloda, oxaliplatin, 5-fluorouracil, and/or leucovorin therapy, EPA + DHA per day potentially prevented weight loss over 9 weeks when compared to standard of care control.(10)

SERIOUS ADVERSE EVENTS

No studies reported serious adverse events attributable to n-3 supplementation, although in two instances with surgical patients for gastric and gastrointestinal cancers, there was improvement in overall postoperative recovery and length of hospital stay, respectively, with parenteral n-3 nutrition. Lung cancer patients supplemented with up to 2.7 g of EPA + DHA were observed to have a better chemotherapy response rate during neoadjuvant therapy. Common side effects of cytotoxic therapies used in breast cancer treatment include febrile neutropenia and neuropathy, and two studies observed a beneficial effect of supplementation on their side effects during neoadjuvant chemotherapy. Metastatic patients supplemented with 1.8 g of DHA per day had decreased neutropenia, anemia, and thrombopenia during cytotoxic chemotherapy. Additionally, when women were supplemented with 1.2 g of EPA + DHA, a decreased risk of peripheral neuropathy incidence over 4 cycles of paclitaxel treatment was observed. These beneficial effects were also observed in palliative esophageal cancer patients, where EPA + DHA supplementation resulted in decreased nausea, thromboembolism, leukopenia, and neutropenia.

IMMUNOLOGICAL OUTCOMES

Enteral or parenteral nutrition is commonly employed for surgical interventions, resulting in elevated inflammation. All studies assessed in this review reported immunological modulations resulting from n-3 fatty acid-enriched enteral/parenteral nutrition. This included improved immune cell response, decreased interleukin (IL)-8, IL-10, and IL-6, modulation of functional capacity and gene expression of immune markers, increased T-lymphocytes, T helper, and natural killer (NK) cells, modulated cytokine production, decreased prostaglandin E2 (PGE2), and reduced incidence of systemic inflammatory response syndrome. C-reactive protein (CRP), a marker of inflammation that is often used as an indicator of poor prognosis, was routinely elevated post-surgery but found to decrease during n-3 supplementation in the days following.

Chemotherapy alters the immune response and inflammatory status, yet evidence of beneficial immunomodulation with n-3 supplementation in non-surgical settings is limited. CRP was the most frequently assessed marker of inflammation, most often in advanced or palliative cancer patients, where it was observed that

capsule/oral n-3 supplementation decreased CRP in head and neck, lung, gastrointestinal, or pancreatic cancers or maintained CRP levels during n-3 supplementation in breast, lung, or pancreatic cancer compared to either baseline levels or increased CRP in non-supplemented controls. Additionally, the CRP/albumin ratio, believed to be a predictor of overall survival in many cancers, was decreased during n-3 supplementation. Other markers reported to be beneficially decreased during n-3 supplementation include IL-6, PGE2, tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF α), and interferon gamma (IFN γ). In a study assessing both localized and advanced colorectal cancer patients, long-term supplementation resulted in a significant decrease in circulating cytokines. Additionally, neutrophil function during chemotherapy improved, CD4/CD8 ratio increased, and percent of CD4+ and CD8+ was maintained compared to elevation in controls.(11)

QUALITY OF LIFE

Changes in life quality have been frequently reported in clinical trial outcomes, and often studies have employed the validated questionnaire from the European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer-Quality of Life Questionnaire-C30. In capsule or oral n-3 supplementation studies, improved perceived quality of life was reported in five studies and improved appetite reported twice—in colorectal and non-small-cell lung cancer studies. Musculoskeletal pain is a well-documented side effect of aromatase inhibitors. In women with previous chemotherapy or radiation and currently on aromatase inhibitors for breast cancer therapy, n-3 per day resulted in a decrease on a pain scale after 30 days. However, a second study in breast cancer patients on aromatase inhibitors found that supplementation with EPA + DHA for 24 weeks only decreased pain significantly in obese patients.

SURVIVAL

Overall survival, progression-free survival, and disease-free survival are key metrics reported in clinical trials. In the current review of the literature, studies investigating the benefits of n-3 supplementation

via enteral/parenteral nutrition did not report on these metrics, likely due to the acute time frame of the interventions. However, a clinical benefit was observed in other studies. Stage III/IV lung cancer patients who received 1.1 g of EPA in a protein enriched oral supplement were reported to have a trend towards progression-free survival. In metastatic patients with a variety of cancers, high doses of n-3 increased survival, which was further increased if stratified between well-nourished and malnourished patients, suggesting that malnutrition could be a predictor that affects n-3 supplementation prolonging survival. Pancreatic patients generally have a median survival of 4.1 months, yet in a study by Wigmore et al., EPA supplementation increased the median survival. In a metastatic breast cancer study where all patients were DHA supplemented, stratification by amount of DHA incorporated into plasma showed that higher DHA incorporation was associated with longer time to progression and overall survival increased. One g of n-3 per day for 51 days increased overall survival and disease-free survival in stage IIIB breast cancer patients. Supplementation with EPA + DHA increased time to progression in colorectal patients and overall long-term survival compared to control in leukemia/lymphoma patients.(6)

ADDITIONAL PARAMETERS

Two of the included studies assessed the Ki67 proliferation index. Ki67 in the tumor is a clinically relevant measure of efficacy in many clinical trials as it is expressed throughout the cell cycle. Darwito et al. found decreased Ki67 expression in breast cancer patients receiving n-3 supplementation, while there were no observed changes in the Ki67 proliferation index in patients with colorectal cancer and liver metastases when supplemented with EPA per day. Other experimentally relevant markers have been assessed in supplementation studies that suggest efficacy of n-3 fatty acids in modulating cancer outcomes including decreased vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and oxidative status, increased glutathione reductase, antioxidant status, superoxide dismutase, and phagocytosis and H₂O₂ in plasma or peripheral blood mononuclear cells and decreased VEGF, carcinoembryonic antigen, and gene expression of matrix metalloproteinase (MMP)-1 and MMP-9 in tumors.(12)

DISCUSSIONS:

This study delves into the intricate effects of eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA), a fish-oil-derived compound, on Molt-4 cells, a subset of T-cell acute lymphoblastic leukemia (T-ALL) characterized by its notorious resistance and grim prognosis. Molt-4 cells, expressing wild-type p53 (wt-p53) and elevated levels of survivin, present a challenging clinical scenario due to their association with poor prognosis in ALL. The research illuminates EPA's impact on these resilient cells, focusing on its induction of apoptosis, potential mechanisms, and selective cytotoxicity compared to normal cells.

In the experimental paradigm, EPA treatment exhibited a remarkable capacity to induce apoptosis in Molt-4 cells, a phenomenon attributed to the activation of caspase-3. Strikingly, this apoptotic response was accompanied by minimal toxicity to normal cells, emphasizing the selective cytotoxicity of EPA—a consistent theme echoed in analogous studies. The study further explored the intricate cellular dynamics influenced by EPA. Notably, a decrease in metabolic activity was observed, suggesting a potential interaction with superoxide dismutase and a consequential impact on mitochondrial function. This multifaceted approach in targeting leukemia cells aligns with the complexity of cancer biology, presenting EPA as a promising candidate for future therapeutic strategies.

A key finding of the study revolves around the modulation of wt-p53, a tumor suppressor protein, by EPA. Elevated wt-p53 levels were noted following EPA treatment, leading to an increased incidence of apoptosis. This observation suggests a p53-dependent mechanism underpinning the apoptotic response to EPA—an aspect that warrants further exploration in deciphering the precise molecular

pathways involved. Furthermore, EPA demonstrated its impact on survivin, a protein associated with anti-apoptotic mechanisms and implicated in the poor prognosis of ALL. The reduction in survivin levels by EPA further facilitated apoptosis, contributing to its antineoplastic effects. A perturbation in the wt-p53 to survivin ratio, orchestrated by EPA treatment, was correlated with heightened apoptotic rates, underscoring the significance of this delicate balance in determining cellular fate. In the clinical context, the study draws attention to the supporting evidence from trials advocating for n-3 supplementation, encompassing both EPA and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), due to their antineoplastic effects. However, the optimal doses and synergistic combinations remain elusive, pointing towards a crucial area for future investigations.

As we navigate the complex landscape of cancer therapeutics, future studies should aim at defining the optimal doses and combinations of n-3 supplementation to bolster clinical recommendations. The multifaceted impact of EPA on key cellular pathways in T-ALL opens avenues for targeted interventions, paving the way for personalized and effective leukemia treatments.

The study focused on the effects of EPA, a fish-oil-derived compound, on Molt-4 cells, a type of T-cell acute lymphoblastic leukemia (T-ALL) known for its resistance and poor prognosis. Molt-4 cells express wt-p53 and high levels of survivin, both associated with poor prognosis in ALL. EPA treatment induced apoptosis in Molt-4 cells through caspase-3 activation, while showing little toxicity to normal cells. This selective cytotoxicity aligns with other studies. EPA also decreased metabolic activity and potentially targeted superoxide dismutase, affecting mitochondrial function. EPA increased wt-p53 protein levels, leading to apoptosis, suggesting a p53-dependent mechanism. EPA also reduced survivin levels, further promoting apoptosis. The ratio of wt-p53 to survivin was perturbed by EPA, correlating with higher apoptotic rates. Clinical trials have supported n-3 supplementation, including EPA and DHA, for its antineoplastic effects, but optimal doses and combinations remain unclear. Future studies should focus on defining these factors to strengthen recommendations.(13)

CONCLUSION:

DHA, an omega-3 fatty acid, has unique properties that make it beneficial in cancer treatment. It incorporates into cellular membranes, produces oxidative products, inhibits cellular enzyme activities, and interacts with cell signaling mediators, all favorably modulating anticancer responses. While other polyunsaturated fatty acids are not expected to behave similarly, DHA has shown promise in basic and preclinical studies, suggesting benefits for cancer patients when combined with chemotherapy or radiotherapy. Clinical trials have reported benefits in cancer-associated symptoms and quality of life, but more patient-based data are needed to recommend regular use of DHA or fish oil. Standardizing clinical protocols is crucial, requiring an international effort involving various stakeholders.(14)

EPA, DHA, and fish oil induce a mitochondrial glycolytic switch, leading to apoptosis and activation of the Nrf2 pathway in AML cells, which enhances cell death, especially when combined with AraC. A phase II clinical trial by the FILO collaborative group is investigating the addition of intravenous fish oil to induction chemotherapy in high-risk AML patients.

The use of n-3 fatty acids (EPA and/or DHA) in clinical settings is supported by strong biological hypotheses and preclinical data. Clinical evidence suggests potential improvements in outcomes important to patients and the disease process. Larger, well-controlled studies with expanded outcomes are needed, along with sufficient doses and durations to test desired outcomes. Future studies should explore cancers where preclinical data suggest efficacy but clinical studies are lacking, such as ovarian cancer.(14)

DHA has emerged as an effective anticancer agent by inducing apoptosis and enhancing drug sensitivity in cancer cells without affecting normal cells. It is oxidized in the cancer cell environment to form DNA

adducts, inducing oxidative DNA damage that triggers apoptosis. DHA also suppresses DNA repair processes and inactivates DNA repair proteins, leading to excess DNA damage and apoptotic signaling in cancer cells. Additionally, DHA increases tumor sensitivity to anticancer drugs by enhancing drug uptake and inhibiting survival signaling, suggesting its potential for cancer prevention and therapy.(15)

REFERENCE

1. Mostafavi E, Zarepour A, Barabadi H, Zarrabi A, Truong LB, Medina-Cruz D. Antineoplastic activity of biogenic silver and gold nanoparticles to combat leukemia: beginning a new era in cancer theragnostic. *Biotechnology Reports*. 2022;34:e00714.
2. Jones CL, Inguva A, Jordan CT. Targeting energy metabolism in cancer stem cells: progress and challenges in leukemia and solid tumors. *Cell stem cell*. 2021;28(3):378-93.
3. Merkle S, Giese E, Rohn S, Karl H, Lehmann I, Wohltmann A, et al. Impact of fish species and processing technology on minor fish oil components. *Food control*. 2017;73:1379-87.
4. Deif MA, Hammam RE, Solyman AA. Gradient boosting machine based on PSO for prediction of leukemia after a breast cancer diagnosis. *International Journal on Advanced Science, Engineering and Information Technology*. 2021;11(2):508-15.
5. Eastham JA, Heller G, Halabi S, Monk III JP, Beltran H, Gleave M, et al. Cancer and Leukemia Group B 90203 (Alliance): radical prostatectomy with or without neoadjuvant chemohormonal therapy in localized, high-risk prostate cancer. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*. 2020;38(26):3042.
6. Shimomura Y, Sobue T, Zha L, Kitamura T, Iwasaki M, Inoue M, et al. Association between meat, fish, and fatty acid intake and incidence of acute myeloid leukemia and myelodysplastic syndrome: the Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective Study. *Environmental Health and Preventive Medicine*. 2023;28:19-.
7. Ashfaq W, Rehman K, Siddique MI, Khan Q-A-A. Eicosapentaenoic acid and docosahexaenoic acid from fish oil and their role in cancer research. *Food Reviews International*. 2020;36(8):795-814.
8. Wang S, Maxwell C, Akella N. Diet as a Potential Moderator for Genome Stability and Immune Response in Pediatric Leukemia. *Cancers* 2021, 13, 413. s Note: MDPI stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published ...; 2021.
9. Wang S, Maxwell CA, Akella NM. Diet as a potential moderator for genome stability and immune response in pediatric leukemia. *Cancers*. 2021;13(3):413.
10. Rey F, Alves E, Gaspar L, Conceição M, Domingues MR. Oils as a source of bioactive lipids (olive oil, palm oil, fish oil). *Bioactive Lipids: Elsevier*; 2023. p. 231-68.
11. Moraes AR, Camargo KC, Simões MO, Ferraz VP, Pereira MT, Evangelista FC, et al. Chemical Composition of Magonia pubescens Essential Oils and Gamma-Radiation Effects on Its Constituents and Cytotoxic Activity in Leukemia and Breast Cancer Model. *Chemistry & Biodiversity*. 2021;18(6):e2100094.
12. Loew A, Köhnke T, Rehbeil E, Pietzner A, Weylandt K-H. A role for lipid mediators in acute myeloid leukemia. *International journal of molecular sciences*. 2019;20(10):2425.
13. de Quadros Camargo C, Mocellin MC, Brunetta HS, Chagas TR, de Souza Fabre ME, de Moraes Trindade EBS, et al. Fish oil decreases the severity of treatment-related adverse events in gastrointestinal cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy: a randomized, placebo-controlled, triple-blind clinical trial. *Clinical nutrition ESPEN*. 2019;31:61-70.
14. Song C, Liu B, Xu P, Xie J, Ge X, Zhou Q, et al. Oxidized fish oil injury stress in Megalobrama amblycephala: Evaluated by growth, intestinal physiology, and transcriptome-based PI3K-Akt/NF- κ B/TCR inflammatory signaling. *Fish & shellfish immunology*. 2018;81:446-55.

15. Zhang T, Ding M, Tao L, Liu L, Tao N, Wang X, et al. Octenyl succinic anhydride modification of bovine bone and fish skin gelatins and their application for fish oil-loaded emulsions. Food Hydrocolloids. 2020;108:106041.